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REDUCING POSTOPERATIVE REINTUBATIONS THROUGH A RISK ASSESSMENT AID

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Importance: Postoperative reintubation (POR) is a major anesthetic adverse event that is defined by the American College of Surgeons National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (ACS NSQIP, 2015) as the unplanned placement of an endotracheal tube or similar airway device within 30 days after surgery with general anesthesia. POR is a serious complication associated with an increase in hospital length of stay, patient morbidity, and mortality. Furthermore, POR is associated with cardiac, pulmonary and renal complications which all often result in increased hospital costs. *Objective:* Develop a risk assessment aid with standardized treatment recommendations based on risk level in order to increase POR awareness and education among anesthesia providers. *Design:* An extensive review of the literature was performed to identify factors associated with POR. Factors were also derived from secondary data analysis from previous DNP project findings. POR factors were then evaluated with the use of a Delphi Study which was deployed to expert participants in the field. *Setting:* Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia, Pasadena, California. *Results:* Three rounds of the Delphi Study were performed, and eleven risk factors were highly associated with POR. A consensus was reached among participants on whether these risk factors put the patient at mild, moderate, or high risk for POR. *Conclusions:* A risk assessment aid and provider recommendations were organized into an infographic. Plans for future implementation were outlined.

Keywords: postoperative reintubation, unexpected intubation, postoperative respiratory failure, risk assessment aid, infographic

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Background

Postoperative reintubation (POR) is a major anesthetic adverse event that is defined by the American College of Surgeons National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (ACS NSQIP, 2015) as the unplanned placement of an endotracheal tube or similar airway device within 30 days after surgery with general anesthesia. Patients are extubated following surgery when airway protection and mechanical ventilation are no longer deemed necessary. However, patients may necessitate reintubation due to hypoxia, hypercapnia, upper airway obstruction, residual neuromuscular blockade (RNMB), nerve injury, mental status changes, or clinical deterioration after surgery (Miskovic & Lumb, 2017; Xie et al., 2022).

Recent studies have identified patient and surgical factors associated with increased risk of reintubation (Acheampong et al., 2018; Xie et al., 2022). A large meta-analysis including over 370,000 patients identified significant risk factors for POR, including American Society of Anesthesiology (ASA) status, several types of surgeries, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), sepsis and deep venous thrombosis (DVT) (Xie et al., 2022). Of these, the most significant risk factor for POR was ASA status, a classification system that reflects a patient's physical condition and severity of co-existing diseases ranging from I (a normal healthy patient) to VI (a patient in which brain death has been declared and will serve as organ donor). Patients with an ASA status greater than or equal to three were found to be 3.58 times more likely to have POR (Xie et al., 2022). This indicates the patient's physical condition plays a prominent role in their ability to recover from general anesthesia (GA).

The surgical site also plays a major role in reintubation risk. Xie and colleagues (2022) demonstrated airway surgeries, head and neck procedures and thoracic cases increased the risk of

POR (2022). Brovman et al. (2017) corroborated similar findings but also added that abdominal and open cases are up to five times more likely to experience POR.

Several strategies exist to decrease the incidence of postoperative pulmonary complications (PPC), including POR. These include performing a comprehensive history and physical (H&P) to investigate medical and surgical factors which may correlate with postoperative complications. Preoperative strategies include educating the patient to medically optimize before surgery, such as encouraging smoking cessation and altering nutrition status (Chandler et al., 2020; Miskovic & Lumb, 2017). Intraoperatively, anesthesia providers can decrease the risk of POR by choosing regional or monitored anesthesia care (MAC) techniques over GA if appropriate, implementing goal-directed fluid therapy, avoiding medications known to cause long-lasting respiratory depression, and proper ventilation management (Chandler et al., 2020). Postoperative strategies include using continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) devices in the Post Anesthesia Care Unit (PACU), early mobilization, and controlling postoperative pain (Miskovic & Lumb, 2017). However, lack of experience and inappropriate anesthesia decision-making has been shown to be linked to POR (Lin et al., 2013). It is essential to educate anesthesia providers on how to adequately screen for POR risk factors and which treatment strategies can be implemented if necessary.

Significance

Although only 1.6% of surgical patients experience POR, it indicates life-threatening respiratory failure, and serious consequences may ensue (Acheampong et al., 2018). Financially, unplanned intubations account for the second most costly postoperative complication, averaging \$26,718 per incident (Merkow et al., 2020). Expenses can further increase as PORs are associated with increased cardiac, pulmonary, and renal complications and postoperative

transfusions (Acheampong et al., 2018). Additionally, POR has been associated with a 17 day increase in hospital stay and a 32% increase in patient mortality (Acheampong et al., 2018). Singer et al. (2019) found that an extended postoperative hospitalization of more than six days was associated with lower patient satisfaction scores, including inadequate explanations from doctors and reduced attentiveness from nurses. Furthermore, negative experiences extend into the recovery period as patients report a postoperative decrease in quality of life and surgery outcome satisfaction after 30 days and one year, respectively (Grigor et al., 2017). Given the various grave repercussions of unplanned reintubation, healthcare providers must take measures to decrease morbidity, mortality, and improve patients' experiences and the bottom-line cost basis of healthcare. One way to accomplish this is through a risk assessment aid with standardized intervention recommendations to optimize clinical decisions (Haritos et al., 2019).

Problem Statement

Although research has identified POR risk factors, these findings must be translated for and available to practitioners in order to be applied in the clinical setting (Xie et al., 2022). Brault et al. (2022) has demonstrated how risk assessment can be highly beneficial in the early identification of patients likely to require POR. Early identification may result in an optimal allocation of resources and treatment modalities (Wallisch et al., 2021). Risk stratification is imperative to the clinical decision-making process and may result in significant changes to the anesthetic plan (Brovman et al., 2022).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this DNP project is to develop a risk assessment aid based on the most current POR risk factors in order to affect practice change. The aims of this project are to

develop standardized treatment recommendations based on risk level to increase awareness and education among anesthesia providers.

Supporting Framework

When conducting EBP, it is essential to utilize a framework to guide clinicians in comprehensively appraising research findings and applying them to the clinical environment (Buckwalter et al., 2017). To optimize outcomes, academic partners and nurses at the University of Iowa collaborated to develop the Iowa Model of Research-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care (Buckwalter et al., 2017). This model has been extensively utilized by clinicians and researchers in over 130 countries to guide the translation of research findings into practice, thus as a known and appreciated model in the EBP community it will be used for this project (Hanrahan et al., 2019). The Iowa Model (Figure 1, Appendix B), based on the Rogers Theory of Diffusion of Innovations, is a heuristic model which incorporates various strategies in a multi-step approach to guide the EBP process (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Repeatedly the Iowa Model has been evaluated as an effective and reliable method of implementing changes in various healthcare settings (Cullen et al., 2023).

The Iowa Model has been successfully utilized as a conceptual framework for many EBP quality improvement projects worldwide. The Iowa Model was used to implement and evaluate a high-fidelity simulation at a large academic medical center to increase Student Registered Nurse Anesthetist (SRNA) skill proficiency with the induction of general anesthesia (Ballister, 2018). The framework allowed the researchers to keep the project narrowly focused by answering the questions in sequence (Ballister, 2018). Furthermore, the framework prompted repeated reflection at various stages of the process, allowing the project to proceed toward its goal (Ballister, 2018). Ultimately, the program promoted basic SRNA proficiency, which increased

operating room efficiency (Ballister, 2018). Howe et al. (2022) also applied the Iowa Model to develop a standardized tool to improve positioning in a Level III Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU). This study demonstrated that optimizing positioning would result in improved postural and musculoskeletal outcomes and enhanced physiologic stability, sensory development, and brain development (Howe et al., 2022). Howe et al. (2022), which included an educational intervention alongside the tool, improved knowledge and positioning scores, again highlighting the effectiveness of this framework in patient outcomes (Howe et al., 2022).

The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care has undergone a multitude of revisions, and the most recently revised version was used to guide the development and implementation of this DNP scholarly project after permission from the Iowa Model Collective (Appendix C). This model pertains directly to clinicians in healthcare and is applicable to hospitals throughout the Kaiser Permanente, Southern California (KPSC) healthcare system (Crawford et al., 2020). The revised Iowa Model consists of seven steps with three decision points designed to guide EBP activities in the healthcare setting. In addition, this model promotes the collaboration of multidisciplinary team members and the engagement of stakeholders (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Detailed description of the steps for the development and implementation of this DNP project, using the Iowa Model as a guide, are described below.

Identifying Triggering Issues and Opportunities

The Iowa Model begins by recognizing a topic for improvement based on an organizational, state, or national problem (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The ACS NSQIP (2021) determined POR as a variable to measure and guide clinicians in improving surgical care quality. Respiratory failure is the primary reason for POR and is associated with increased morbidity, mortality, and hospital length of stay (Acheampong et al., 2018). Additionally, this complication

results in increased costs and poor patient satisfaction (Singer et al., 2019). Given the numerous serious consequences, Kaiser Permanente has identified POR as an essential topic for the organization to investigate further.

State the Question or Purpose

The second step in the Iowa model entails formally stating the question or purpose of the project to enable a focused direction (Buckwalter et al., 2017). This DNP project aimed to develop a risk assessment aid with a standardized list of recommendations according to the patient's level of risk. The project analyzed risk factors for the aid based on the NSQIP data collected from previous DNP projects and the extensive literature review performed by this DNP project. The risk factors were analyzed via a Delphi study.

First Decision Point: Is This Topic a Priority?

The first decision point in the revised Iowa Model includes determining the priority of the topic, as less critical projects receive fewer resources and are thus harder to implement (Buckwalter et al., 2017). POR's result in negative consequences to the patient and are detrimental to the hospital, organization, and healthcare system. KPSA decided the research on POR is a topic of high priority to identify trends, improve patient outcomes and reduce costs.

Form a Team

Forming a team to work on the project is the next step in the Iowa framework. For this DNP project, team members included three nurse anesthesia students and two Ph.D. faculty advisors. Faculty advisors from CSUF and KPSA guided the students and provided expert opinions throughout each component of the DNP project. Before beginning this project, students took classes in research, EBP, informatics, and quality improvement. Additionally, all students have a bachelor's degree in nursing and clinical experience in the field.

Assemble, Appraise, and Synthesize Body of Evidence

The fourth step in the Iowa Model includes conducting a systematic literature search and synthesizing evidence found from relevant studies. The team performed a comprehensive review of the literature on the following topics: POR factors, the effectiveness of risk assessment tools, existing aids: costs and provider acceptance, recommendations for decreasing the rate of POR, and implementation strategies. After evaluation of the aggregate literature, reoccurring findings were identified and analyzed for inclusion in the risk assessment aid and recommendations.

Second Decision Point: Is There Sufficient Evidence?

The second decision point in the Iowa Model involves assessing current evidence to determine if a practice change is needed or if more research is needed. Previous DNP project teams and this DNP project team performed an extensive review of the literature and found sufficient evidence that a practice change is needed to increase anesthesia provider awareness of risk factors associated with POR. The evidence also supports the use of a risk assessment aid presented as an infographic to convey important information and improve informed decision-making among providers.

Design and Pilot a Practice Change

The fifth step in the Iowa Model involves pilot testing the practice change on a small scale. This DNP project designed a risk assessment aid and gathered expert feedback on the aid via a Delphi study to make recommendations on identifying and preventing POR. This DNP project recommends future projects pilot the risk assessment aid at a Kaiser facility in Southern California. CRNAs and Anesthesiologists should receive education on the importance of decreasing the incidence of POR to improve care safety and reduce costs related to POR. Staff

should also be educated on how to utilize the risk assessment aid and encouraged to participate in the implementation of the tool into practice.

Third Decision Point: Is the change Appropriate for Adoption?

The final decision point in the Iowa Model guides the team to determine if the practice change is appropriate for adoption into practice. The DNP project recommends future projects disseminate pre- and post-education questionnaires to anesthesia providers to determine if the implementation improves anesthesia provider awareness of POR and assess how likely providers are to use the risk assessment aid in their practice.

Integrate and Sustain the Practice Change

The sixth step in the Iowa Model aims to identify factors influencing sustained practice change. These factors include identification and buy-in of key stakeholders, identifying cultural or systemic factors so that the change may be embedded into the system, and continuous monitoring of process and outcome measurements such as staff compliance, cost, and patient outcomes. Key stakeholders will need to be identified and embedding the change into practice will depend on the understanding of CRNAs as well as their appreciation of POR clinical significance. Recommendations to maintain and increase compliance with the risk assessment aid are included in this DNP project.

Disseminate Results

The last step in the Iowa Model involves disseminating the results from the practice change implementation. The results from this DNP project were shared at several healthcare conferences. Targeted audiences include anesthesia providers such as Anesthesiologists and CRNA's, postoperative care nurses and operating room staff.

Review of Literature

Overview

The purpose of this literature review is to emphasize the importance and determine current practices of a standardized risk aid and recommendation list to decrease the incidence of POR. The review contains five sections: POR factors, effectiveness of risk assessment tools, existing aids: costs and provider acceptance, recommendations for decreasing the rate of postoperative intubations and implementation strategies.

A search of the literature was performed using PubMed, Cochrane Review, CINAHL, OVID, and Google Scholar databases. The search terms used to retrieve relevant literature were “postoperative reintubation,” “unplanned reintubation,” “risk factors,” “predisposing factors,” “patient factors,” “surgical factors,” “risk assessment tools,” “risk assessment scales,” “provider adherence,” “practitioner acceptance,” “effectiveness,” “patient outcomes,” “health outcomes,” “patient safety,” “cost analysis,” “affordability,” “financial burden,” “implementation strategies,” “recommendations,” “postoperative pulmonary complications,” and “prevention”. The search was limited to peer-reviewed articles, published in the English language between 2016 and 2023. Additionally, studies that assessed reintubation factors related to the intensive care unit (ICU) patient populations were excluded. A total of 52 articles, 14 qualitative and 38 quantitative, were utilized for this literature review. The quantitative studies included 9 systematic reviews, 4 RCTs, 1 observational study, 9 case-control studies, and 15 cohort studies.

Postoperative Reintubation Factors

Several risk factors for POR have been found to be associated with a patient's medical history and physical status including ASA status, pulmonary disease, sepsis, and advanced age. One of the more prominent findings is ASA status \geq III (Acheampong et al., 2018; Banik et al.,

2021; Chen et al., 2021). ASA classification is a risk index that indicates a patient's physical health on a scale from I (healthy) to VI (declared brain dead). A patient classified as $ASA \geq III$ has a severe systemic disease that limits physical function, such as advanced heart or lung disease, end-stage renal disease, or morbid obesity. Xie et al. (2022) performed a systematic review and meta-analysis to determine the most influential risk factors associated with POR and found $ASA \geq III$ was the most prominent risk factor. Severe systemic disease impedes a patient's ability to recover from anesthesia and puts the patient at increased risk for respiratory complications, which are associated with POR (Miskovic & Lumb, 2017).

Pulmonary diseases such as COPD and pneumonia are also associated with an increased risk of POR (Banik et al., 2021; Haritos et al., 2019; Xie et al., 2022). This may be due to abnormal respiratory bronchiole function, leading to increased airway resistance and respiratory muscle weakness in the postoperative period, which puts a patient at an increased risk for reintubation (Miskovic & Lumb, 2017). Sepsis has also been linked to an increased incidence of POR (Chen et al., 2021; Xie et al., 2022). The risk for POR in patients with sepsis was over ten times higher than in those without sepsis (Xie et al., 2022). Acheampong et al. (2018) also reported a statistically significant POR risk for patients with sepsis undergoing major general and vascular surgery ($p < 0.01$). This may be because sepsis is associated with hemodynamic instability and pulmonary dysfunction, which increase the risk for pulmonary complications like POR.

Advanced age was associated with POR in several studies; Li et al. (2017) reported a statistically significant effect of age > 60 on POR risk ($p < 0.05$) among patients undergoing cervical spine surgery. Chen et al. (2021) reported similar findings in a case-control study comparing various surgical cases. However, Xie et al. (2022) found no association between age

> 65 and POR after GA. Elderly patients are known to metabolize anesthetic drugs more slowly and are more sensitive to anesthetics, necessitating vigilant monitoring (Olotu, 2021). These findings provide that a patient's physical condition influences their POR risk. Based on this body of literature, this DNP project assessed targeted patient factors such as ASA status, COPD, pneumonia, sepsis, and advanced age > 65 for inclusion in the risk assessment aid.

Several studies reported correlations between surgical factors and POR. Xie et al. (2022) found statistically significant associations between thoracic, airway, head and neck, and emergency surgeries and POR ($p < 0.001$). In a large retrospective study, Haritos et al. (2019) reported that emergency surgery and surgery involving the abdomen, thorax, or airway were associated with POR (Haritos et al., 2019). Similarly, Chen et al. (2021) found that head and neck and thoracic surgery were associated with unplanned reintubation in a retrospective case-control study. Surgeries of the head, neck, airway and thorax may compromise pulmonary function or lead to airway obstruction, which may necessitate POR. Li et al. (2017) and Banik et al. (2021) found that longer surgical duration was associated with increased POR risk. However, Xie et al. (2022) did not investigate this relationship in their meta-analysis and this factor necessitates further research before conclusions can be made.

The paralytic agent rocuronium may also increase POR (Feltracco et al., 2016). In a randomized controlled study, rocuronium was reported to have a longer duration of action than cisatracurium, another paralytic, and was associated with a RNMB incidence rate of 15% in PACU after reversal with neostigmine (Feltracco et al., 2016). RNMB is associated with POR, and providers must be aware of the risks of inadequate reversal of muscle relaxants (Miskovic & Lumb, 2017). A study that surveyed over 1,600 anesthesiologists found anesthesiologists were overconfident in their knowledge of neuromuscular monitoring when answering true/false

questions related to the topic (Naguib et al., 2019). A gap in knowledge regarding neuromuscular blocking agents and adequate reversal is concerning because RNMB is associated with POR (Miskovic & Lumb, 2017). Based on this body of literature, this DNP project assessed surgical factors such as emergency surgery, surgery of the thorax, airway, head and neck, and use of neuromuscular blockade with rocuronium for inclusion in the risk assessment aid.

Effectiveness of Risk Assessment Aids

Risk assessment aids are valuable tools to improve patient safety by identifying patients at increased risks of adverse events who may benefit from targeted treatments (Stones & Yates, 2018). Risk assessment aids are important because clinical judgment is not a reliable predictor of risk alone (Wong et al., 2020). Risk assessment aids are effective in various healthcare settings (Deslate et al., 2021; Grau et al., 2019). Barker et al. (2022) developed and implemented an evidence-based risk assessment aid for post-extubation dysphagia (PED) in the ICU. The aid was developed by critical care team members and underwent multiple variations based on staff feedback. After implementation, patient PED screenings nearly doubled, nurses reported increased awareness of factors associated with PED, and PED referrals to the hospital specialty team increased (Barker et al., 2022). Similarly, Deslate et al. (2021) implemented a STOP-BANG risk screening score to identify patients at high risk of obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) in an ambulatory gastrointestinal center. Patients in this ambulatory center typically underwent procedures that did not necessitate an advanced airway, but received anesthetics that caused respiratory depression. Patients with OSA are more sensitive to the respiratory depressive effects of anesthetics, and are more at risk for hypoxia, failed extubation, unplanned ICU admissions, and increased PACU length of stay (Leong et al., 2018). STOP-BANG is a validated instrument used to detect patients at risk of OSA (Chung et al., 2016). After the STOP-BANG

implementation, providers could better predict intraprocedural airway complications and found the tool had high validity in predicting an increased need for airway maneuvers (Deslate et al., 2021).

In the perioperative setting, risk assessment aids help identify risks for morbidity and mortality (Stones & Yates, 2018). Several types of risk assessment aids exist, the most common being risk assessment scores and risk assessment models. Risk assessment scores assign a numerical weight to risk factors associated with a patient outcome. Scoring systems are easy to use, accurate and easily accessible to providers yet they do not provide individualized risk predictions of the adverse outcome (Stones & Yates, 2018). Risk assessment models tend to be more comprehensive, yet time consuming and complex (Stones & Yates, 2018). ASA status is perhaps the most well-known risk assessment score used in anesthesia. More complex risk model systems exist, yet ASA remains the most influential due to its ease of use and accuracy in predicting postoperative complications and mortality after non-cardiac surgery (Stones & Yates, 2018).

Infographics make conceptualizing information more effective by presenting the information in an organized and visually appealing manner (Bystrova, 2020). This helps learners perceive and memorize the information presented quickly. Buljan et al. (2018) demonstrated that infographics are effective in translating knowledge from systematic reviews. Buljan et al. (2020) found that professional audiences preferred infographics over other methods of presenting information due to its appreciable reading experience and user-friendliness. Infographics are also beneficial for material that has a cause-effect relationship because they can be well structured and easily connected (Bystrova, 2020).

In conclusion, risk assessment tools help providers identify potential patient safety hazards, promote more vigilant monitoring, and improve informed decision-making. This DNP project created a risk assessment aid in the form of an infographic with risk stratification because of its ease of use, simpler implementation into clinical practice, and accuracy in predicting adverse patient outcomes.

Existing Aids: Costs and Provider Acceptance

Costs

Postoperative reintubations are not only unfavorable due to increases in morbidity and mortality, but are also associated with a marked increase in healthcare cost (Acheampong et al., 2018). Postoperative pulmonary complications (PPC) in hospitalized patients may result in up to an overall 47% increase in cost (Miskovic & Lumb, 2017). Haritos et al. (2019) reported that their calculated median hospital cost was approximately \$7.2 million for just 89 cases of reintubation after planned extubation. As a multicenter randomized controlled trial, Haritos et al. (2019) indicated that preoperative risk assessment and education may result in avoiding the financial costs related to respiratory complications postoperatively.

In order to reduce the financial ramifications related to the patient morbidity/mortality, the American College of Surgeons National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (ACS NSQIP) data will be utilized. Two Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia (KPSA)/California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) DNP cohorts performed a secondary analysis using the ACS NSQIP database to determine patient and surgical risk factors highly associated with unplanned intubations. According to Stone and Yates (2018), the ACS NSQIP which utilizes 21 preoperative factors to predict 14 post-surgical adverse outcomes, has been demonstrated to be accurate. Similarly, Liu et al., (2016) showed that the NSQIP Surgical Risk Calculator model

calibration and discrimination provides an accurate assessment of patients' surgical risk. This project analyzed risk factors detected through the NSQIP database before creating the risk assessment aid.

Numerous studies have demonstrated the efficacy of utilizing predictive risk assessment aids to decrease healthcare expenditures (Avşar & Karadağ, 2018; Grau et al., 2019; Pehora et al. (2020). Pehora et al. (2020) evaluated their own predictive model in order to predict which patients would likely experience perioperative respiratory adverse events (PRAE) and require specialist anesthesia care. Their model, developed from generalized estimating questions (GEE), successfully identified patients at low risk of PRAEs who could be safely managed in a cost-effective community hospital or ambulatory setting (Pehora et al., 2020). The GEE model was suggested to also relieve the economic burden of polysomnography overreliance to assess risks and make informed preoperative decisions (Pehora et al., 2020). The model accurately identified low risk patients who would not benefit from costly increased levels of monitoring, potential admission to intensive care facilities, and allocation of other healthcare resources. (Pehora et al., 2020).

Grau et al. (2019) also designed and implemented a pulmonary screening tool and intervention protocol to prevent pulmonary complications in patients undergoing total joint arthroplasties. After implementation of the risk assessment tool and educational sessions on utilization, pulmonary complication rates decreased from 5.7% to 0.09% (Grau et al., 2019). Grau et al. (2019) also reported improved patient satisfaction and decreased healthcare expenditure by approximately \$50,000 per patient that no longer necessitated postoperative ICU admission. In non-surgical settings, implementation of a risk assessment tool and intervention recommendations for pressure ulcers and incontinence associated dermatitis was found to

decrease the incidence of tissue breakdown and decreased hospital costs (Avşar & Karadağ, 2018). The study utilized a control group and intervention group; the latter received educational sessions regarding the risk index tool and treatment strategies. After implementation, the researchers reported the incidence of tissue integrity deterioration was 18.2% compared to 54.5% in the control group (Avşar & Karadağ, 2018). The intervention group did report an increase in daily average healthcare costs per patient related to the use of prevention equipment, treatment modalities and nursing time. However, pressure ulcer treatment in the control group far exceeded prevention costs implemented in the intervention group, resulting in an overall healthcare savings (Avşar & Karadağ, 2018). In toto, these studies illustrate the beneficial financial implications of utilizing screening tools (Avşar & Karadağ, 2018; Pehora et al., 2020).

Provider Acceptance

After developing the risk assessment aid, it is vital to ascertain providers' perceptions of the aid and confirm its usability. La Guardia et al. (2019) examined providers' perceptions towards a competency-based training in the healthcare setting regarding suicide risk assessment. Overall, providers reported an increase in adequacy of training as well as confidence in treating these patients (La Guardia et al., 2019). Providers also suggested a need for continued additional focus regarding suicide risk assessment and prevention (La Guardia et al., 2019). In another study that preoperatively utilized the Surgical Risk Preoperative Assessment System (SURPAS), Bronsert et al. (2020) would initiate additional discussion regarding surgical patients at high risk for adverse outcomes. After the roll out of this tool, the authors observed an overall improvement in patient understanding and surgeon confidence, which were even more pronounced amongst cases with higher risk estimates. Lastly, Goodin et al., (2020), which utilizes the Prescription Drug Monitoring Program (PDMPs) to assess risk of opioid-related harms, illustrated how 87%

of the obstetricians and gynecologists responded positively regarding the effectiveness of PDMPs as a primary tool to reduce abuse and diversion.

While risk assessment aids are generally positively perceived by providers, there are a variety of barriers that this project aimed to overcome in order to create a sustainable intervention. Souli et al., (2018) noted healthcare personnel have negative perceptions regarding a violence risk assessment for patients suffering from mental illness. Only 62% of the providers included in the study reported using the risk assessment tool at all, none of them having used it daily (Souli et al., 2018). Barriers to utilizing the risk assessment tools include a lack of resources, time, and knowledge of the tool, along with negative attitudes towards the patients (Souli et al., 2018). Barriers related to reimbursement, cost, resistance to change, lack of scientific validation, and the difficulty of changing patient health behaviors were also reported in the literature (Thyvalikakath et al., 2018). Pradhan et al., (2022) found that preoperative risk assessment calculators were not as useful for predicting mortality, major complications, and post-surgical infections if they were not integrated into the electronic health system. These articles highlight how crucial it is to identify the provider specific facilitators and barriers in order to provide direction for a lasting intervention.

Recommendations for Decreasing the Rate of Postoperative Reintubations

Although the literature has identified patient and surgical risk factors for POR, information guiding the provider's care in the perioperative setting to decrease the incidence of POR in surgical patients is non-existent. Therefore, expanding the literature search to include recommendations for decreasing the incidence of PPC's was necessary to determine the state of knowledge on this issue. The European Society of Anesthesiologist and European Society of Intensive Care Medicine defines PPC as one of the following conditions: respiratory infection,

respiratory failure, pleural effusion, atelectasis, pneumothorax, bronchospasm, and aspiration pneumonia (Jammer et al., 2015). These complications typically lead to impaired gas exchange resulting in hypoxemia or hypercapnia (Barash et al., 2017). Depending on the severity of respiratory compromise, an endotracheal tube (ETT) may be necessary to provide mechanical ventilation (Barash et al., 2017). Therefore, prevention strategies encompassing all forms of PPC are imperative to decrease the incidence of POR.

Currently, no standardized practice exists to decrease the incidence of PPC (Tegegne et al., 2021). However, multiple studies recognize the need for screening surgical patients using a risk assessment tool to predict the development of postoperative respiratory failure (Miskovic & Lumb, 2017; Ruscic et al., 2017). Identification of high-risk patients allows for a thorough evaluation, documentation of comorbidities, and allocation of necessary resources before the patient enters the surgical facility (Chandler et al., 2020; Ruscic et al., 2017). Low risk patients should receive the standard of care; however, initiating a prevention protocol for high-risk patients during the perioperative period is necessary to decrease their likelihood of developing a complication (Tegegne et al., 2021). Additionally, patients with two or more risk factors should receive a chest x-ray preoperatively to ensure the provider has thoroughly evaluated the patient before surgery (Tegegne et al., 2021). If the results do not show any unexpected findings, surgery can proceed. However, if an abnormal finding is present and the surgery is elective, it should be postponed as further investigation is necessary.

Moreover, patients and providers should mitigate modifiable risk before surgery, including promotion of smoking cessation four weeks before surgery and optimizing severe anemia through transfusions, supplements, epoetin alfa injections or a combination of the aforementioned therapies (Chandler et al., 2020; Miskovic & Lumb, 2017; Tegegne et al., 2021).

To improve lung conditioning before surgery, several publications tout that patients should prepare by beginning inspiratory muscle training two weeks before surgery by blowing into a glove three times a day (Chandler et al., 2020; Tegegne et al., 2021). Helping patients achieve a prime health status is beneficial, as certain disease states are associated with an increased risk of developing a PPC. Unfortunately, the literature states patients should improve modifiable risk factors before surgery, but the same studies lack information on the overall impact optimization has on patient outcome and overall costs.

Prophylactic chest physiotherapy on the day of surgery has also been documented to decrease the incidence of PPC by aiding in pulmonary endurance and expulsion of secretions (Boden et al., 2018; Odor et al., 2020; Tegegne et al., 2021). Staff should provide 30 minutes of chest physiotherapy, or patients should perform deep respirations in the preoperative area as suggested measures to decrease the incidence of PPC (Tegegne et al., 2021). In fact, a 30-minute preoperative chest physiotherapy session was reported to decrease the incidence of PPC by 50% (Boden et al., 2018). Additionally, perioperative staff should take special consideration for patients with existing pulmonary diseases, which includes providing preoperative continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) for patients with OSA and salbutamol therapy for patients with asthma (Tegegne et al., 2021). Both OSA and asthmatic patient populations may be at higher risk for developing PPC, thus optimization of both of these chronic conditions could benefit from preoperative interventions to decrease the chances of developing problems postoperatively (Tegegne et al., 2021).

The best anesthetic technique to decrease the incidence of PPC remains to be determined and can be influenced by many aspects of the anesthetic; however, providers should avoid general anesthesia (GA) for high risk patients if possible (Tegegne et al., 2021). Overall, regional

anesthesia is more favorable than GA in any patient with a questionable airway or in patients with lung pathophysiology, as it does not require airway manipulation and has a lesser impact on ventilation (Chandler et al., 2020; Miskovic & Lumb, 2017). Conversely, using a supraglottic airway decreases the risk of emergent POR compared to an ETT, likely due to the absence of neuromuscular blockade (NMB) with these types of devices and this style of inhalational gas delivery (Hammer et al., 2021). RNMB renders the patient weak and without control of many of the muscles required for effective ventilatory oxygen exchange (Alenezi et al., 2021). Not surprising, residual paralysis is also associated with significantly more postoperative critical respiratory events, with the incidence varying between 53% and 75% in post-surgical patients (Alenezi et al., 2021; Fu et al., 2018). Without the use of all muscle function and tone, patients will not only fail to breathe effectively, but can suffer the consequences of not being able to cough, clear secretions or protect their own airway and prevent aspiration; in all of these instances, RNMB predisposes the patient to suffer PPC (Alenezi et al., 2021).

Prevention of RNMB requires a multifaceted approach which includes careful medication selection, vigilant patient monitoring, and adequate reversal of the drug used to induce NMB. If neuromuscular blocking agents are necessary to provide paralysis due to the nature of the surgical procedure, practitioners should use short and intermediate-acting rather than long-acting agents (Tegege et al., 2021). Medications with a short duration of action may prevent a lingering effect of the drug, as patients undergoing a short surgery have a higher incidence of RNMB (Aenezi et al., 2021). Additional preventative measures include using a RNMB prediction score which is a 15-point scale based on identified risk factors with the aims of determining which patients are at high risk of postoperative RNMB (Patrocínio et al., 2021). A high score correlates to an increased risk of developing a PPC. Providers should use the PPC

prediction score as a screening tool for identifying patients and further evaluate with a quantitative nerve stimulator monitoring device to determine the level of NMB (Patrocínio et al., 2021). This method of utilizing the PPC prediction score not only helps determine which patient is at risk for PPC, but ultimately may help foster an overall efficient, safe anesthesia practice. In fact, ensuring providers assess the NMB status of all patients with a nerve stimulator monitoring device intraoperatively and/or before extubation can decrease the incidence of RNMB in any patient (Alenezi et al., 2021; Domenech et al., 2019). Although a train-of-four (TOF) ratio measurement with a nerve stimulator is a common assessment of the level of RNMB, it is not foolproof or completely without error. Literature demonstrates that a significant decrease in pulmonary function test performance can be detected at each TOF value; this suggests adequate lung recovery (sometimes referred to as 85% of preoperative baseline lung function) does not occur even with the recommended TOF value of 0.9 (Fu et al., 2018). Therefore, practitioners should administer a reversal agent to all patients who receive a neuromuscular blocking agent to ensure complete return of lung function in the postoperative period. Further research is necessary to establish the best approach to monitor for full recovery of NMB with the most accurate and clinically relevant results for practitioners.

In addition to assessing NMB, the anesthesia provider must decide whether to administer a reversal agent. Although Domenech et al. (2019) found a lower incidence of PPC in patients who received sugammadex, Aenezi et al. (2021) found a high incidence of RNMB despite 77% of the study population receiving neostigmine; thus, the selection of a reversal agent may influence patient outcomes. Some evidence shows that the incidence of PPC does not vary based on the type of reversal drug given (Li et al., 2021). However, a large multicenter cohort study showed that in comparison to neostigmine, sugammadex reversal reduced pulmonary

complications by 30%, and decreased risk of pneumonia and respiratory failure by 47% and 55%, respectively (Kheterpal et al., 2020). Additionally, an extensive amount of high-level evidence reports a lower incidence of PPC when sugammadex is administered compared to neostigmine in the reversal of NMB (Wang et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2022).

A vast majority of the literature agrees that when administering GA with an ETT, ventilation of the patient should commence using low tidal volumes (6-8 ml/kg), with a peak end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) of 5 cmH₂O. These parameters decrease the incidence in PPC and have been found to have a protective effect on the lungs (Deng et al., 2020; Miskovic and Lumb; 2017; Tegegne et al., 2021; Odor et al., 2020;). Lung protective ventilation mitigates atelectasis and overdistension by keeping transpulmonary pressures low (Rusic et al., 2017). If ventilation is inadequate, adding recruitment maneuvers and increasing PEEP have been shown to be the best approach for improving the patient's pulmonary condition (Miskovic & Lumb, 2017).

An additional intraoperative management strategy to decrease PPC includes goal-directed fluid management using measures such as heart rate, blood pressure, and urine output as a guide for addressing intraoperative fluid shifts (Tegegne et al., 2021). This approach protects against the negative consequences of giving too much or too little fluid which may include impaired oxygen delivery, acquiring infections, ischemia, pulmonary edema, and reperfusion injury (Tegegne et al., 2021). Odor et al. (2020) found goal-directed hemodynamic therapy demonstrated moderate evidence of decreasing PPC with a 25% relative risk reduction.

During maintenance, De la Gala et al. (2017) found a higher incidence of PPC with propofol than sevoflurane, likely due to the increase in lung and systemic inflammatory response, as evidenced by an increase in pro-inflammatory cytokines. However, conflicting

evidence from additional studies showed no difference in PPC incidence between using sevoflurane and total intravenous anesthesia during the maintenance phase of anesthesia (Lee et al., 2022; Zhang & Wang, 2017).

Postoperatively, PACU staff should continuously monitor the pulse oximeter, administer humidified oxygen as needed and maintain a high-level alert for pulmonary complications (Tegegne et al., 2021). Additionally, various prophylactic non-invasive ventilation techniques benefit a small group of high risk patients as it decreases atelectasis by increasing the alveolar surface area, leading to improved ventilation and oxygenation (Miskovic & Lumb, 2017; Tegegne et al., 2021). Prophylactic postoperative CPAP reduces PPC in all patients undergoing major abdominal and thoracic surgeries (Odor et al., 2020). Furthermore, surgical patients with OSA benefit from the administration of CPAP in the initial postoperative period (Tegegne et al., 2021). Similarly, a prophylactic high-flow nasal cannula (HFNC) decreases the risk of reintubation in the immediate postoperative period for high risk patients undergoing cardiothoracic surgery (Chaudhuri et al., 2020). In addition to these various oxygen therapies, other postoperative interventions to reduce PPC include elevating the head of the bed more than 20 degrees (if not contraindicated secondary to the surgery) to optimize functional residual capacity of the lungs (Tegegne et al., 2021). Administering a prophylactic mucolytic treatment during the first few days postoperatively and encouraging early ambulation may also be beneficial by aiding in the mobilization of airway secretions (Miskovic & Lumb, 2017; Tegegne et al., 2021). Additionally, patients at high risk for developing PPC who undergo abdominal operations may benefit from prophylactic postoperative nasogastric decompression to facilitate optimal respirations and decrease the risk of aspiration (Tegegne et al., 2021).

Postoperative pain control is imperative to decrease the incidence of PPC, as inadequate management can result in splinting, sputum retention, and infection (Tegegne et al., 2021). Adequate analgesia, particularly when achieved with neuraxial blocks (spinals and epidurals), decreases PPCs when compared to traditional management with intravenous narcotics (Tegegne et al., 2021). When administering neuraxial anesthesia, providers should aim to limit intravenous narcotic and sedative medications as they can reduce respiratory strength (Tegegne et al., 2021). Pain management with an epidural, when indicated, should be utilized as it improves PPC outcomes when compared to morphine patient-controlled analgesia (Odor et al., 2020).

In conclusion, a preoperative risk assessment is crucial for identifying high risk patients and subsequently leading the practitioner to modify perioperative care to decrease the incidence of PPC (Ruscic et al., 2017; Tegegne et al., 2021). Although many strategies have shown to be individually beneficial, implementing a set of standardized interventions (while tailoring care to specific patient comorbidities and surgical requirements) may be the best approach for healthcare facilities (Odor et al., 2020). Implementation of a standardized pulmonary care bundle that included smoking cessation, chest physiotherapy, incentive spirometry, adequate pain control, early mobilization, and aspiration precautions yielded significant reduction in pneumonia and unplanned intubation among surgical cancer patients (Jalil et al., 2021). Furthermore, implementing an enhanced recovery surgery (ERAS) pathway, which included a combination of protocolized care, reduced PPC (Odor et al., 2020). This doctoral project created a risk assessment aid and provided recommendations grounded in the best evidence-based practice (EBP) to guide providers while caring for high-risk patients to decrease the incidence of POR.

Implementation Strategies

Educational sessions as a stand-alone intervention have demonstrated inadequacy in changing practice and clinical outcomes (Cassidy et al., 2021). A systematic review showed that multi-component implementation strategies that included educational sessions combined with other techniques (organizational policy changes, staff participation, and posting of visual educational materials) were found to be correlated with successful project implementations (Cassidy et al., 2021). Another systematic review revealed nurses have positive attitudes regarding EBP implementations, but significant barriers such as inadequate time and resources, short training sessions, and lack of supportive workplace culture hinder EBP implementation success (Li et al., 2019). Similar findings concerning barriers to implementation were corroborated by another systematic review (Lau et al., 2016). The latter review also showed that ease of integration into the current system, staff involvement, and evidence of implementation benefit were critical factors to successful practice change implementation. Additional barriers to implementation include a culture resistant to change, inadequate stakeholder buy-in, lack of resources, and inability to adapt to pre-existing conditions (Lau et al., 2016). Understanding and identifying the driving factors and barriers to implementation are key to affecting successful practice change (Lau et al., 2016; Li et al., 2019).

Lewin's Change Theory Model states that long-lasting change involves changing current attitudes, motivations, and behaviors (Lewin, 1947). See Table 1, Appendix A for a visual representation of the three steps (Unfreeze, Change, Freeze) of Lewin's Change Theory Model. Several studies implemented Lewin's Change Theory Model while implementing a risk assessment aid for nursing staff (Grass & Bundy, 2021; Huang et al., 2020). Grass and Bundy (2021) implemented and evaluated the effectiveness of the Apfel Post Discharge Nausea and

Vomiting Risk Assessment tool for postoperative nausea and vomiting and used Lewin's Change Theory Model to identify key stakeholders and unit champions. After implementation, 92% of staff complied within the set time frame, exceeding their goal of 80% (Grass & Bundy, 2021).

Similarly, in a hematology-oncology unit, Huang et al. (2020) adopted Lewin's Change Theory to facilitate practice change in their oral care regimen. After implementation, patients who received education regarding oral care increased from 23% to 98%, and those who followed oral hygiene protocols increased from 27% to 96% (Huang et al., 2020). In conclusion, this DNP project proposed using multi-component implementation strategies such as educational sessions with staff participation, identification and buy-in of key stakeholders, and careful analysis of primary drivers and barriers to the implementations' success. In addition, to promote long-lasting change, this DNP project encouraged the integration of Lewin's Change Theory Model for strategies to understand and change unit cultures, attitudes, and behaviors.

Conclusion

A patient's physical condition and type of surgery influence their risk of POR. Based on this body of literature, this DNP project assessed patient factors such as ASA status, pulmonary disease, sepsis, advanced age, type of surgical procedure, and use of muscle relaxation for inclusion in the risk assessment aid. While this DNP project did not disseminate a risk assessment aid into clinical practice, recommendations have been provided for future projects on how to successfully implement this POR risk assessment aid into practice. Recommendations include the use of multi-component implementation strategies such as educational sessions combined with policy change, stakeholder buy-in, and staff participation.

During the preoperative evaluation, providers must recognize high risk patients to provide interventions that decrease their chance of developing PPC thus requiring POR.

Preoperative care may include obtaining a chest x-ray to ensure the absence of abnormalities, optimizing modifiable risk factors, and providing instructions on inspiratory muscle training. Once the patient arrives at the hospital, the administration of prophylactic chest physiotherapy, salbutamol treatment to patients with asthma, and CPAP to patients with OSA before surgery has been shown to decrease complications postoperatively (Tegegne et al., 2021). If possible, the anesthetist should avoid GA with an ETT during surgery, as it is associated with increased RNMB and PPC (Tegegne et al., 2021). However, if the procedure necessitates GA, anesthetists should use lung protective ventilation, and providers should monitor the patient's level of NMB, keeping in mind that an adequate TOF ratio does not depict full pulmonary recovery (Fu et al., 2018). Therefore, providers should highly consider administering sugammadex to patients receiving an aminosteroid neuromuscular blocking agent who do not have any contraindications, as it provides superior reversal compared to neostigmine (Kheterpal et al., 2020). Additionally, providers should utilize goal-directed fluid therapy. Postoperatively applying non-invasive ventilation, elevating the head of the bed, administering a mucolytic, and ensuring early mobility should be performed for high-risk patients. Lastly, providers should achieve adequate postoperative pain management by using neuraxial blocks or epidurals when indicated. Miskovic & Lumb (2017) also found that patients who received central or peripheral regional anesthesia had a reduced incidence in PPC. Utilizing a perioperative care bundle has decreased the incidence of PPC (Odor et al., 2020, Jalil et al., 2021). This project created a set of recommendations to guide providers' care for high-risk patients to decrease POR incidence.

A substantial number of high-level evidence articles were used in this literature review, including meta-analyses, meta-syntheses, systematic reviews, RCTs, cohort, and observational studies. The studies were organized and thorough when describing the purpose, inclusion and

exclusion criteria, and variable definitions. Methods were well designed to minimize limitations and were reported with enough detail to be replicated by another researcher. Results and conclusions were concise and clear, facilitating the integration of findings into this literature review. Recurrent limitations of the articles included small sample sizes and lack of randomization or variable control. However, the studies' strengths outweigh the limitations, which enabled utilization of the results in the literature review. Findings congruent among articles were analyzed for inclusion in the risk assessment aid and recommendations to decrease the incidence of POR.

Methods

This section will describe the process of developing the risk assessment aid in an effort to increase awareness of POR among anesthesia providers. The design of the project, setting and participants, data collection, data analysis, and ethical considerations will be discussed.

Information gathered from the literature review along with secondary data derived from previous DNP projects' NSQIP analysis provided the assessed POR risk factors. These factors were evaluated through the use of a three-round Delphi study. The results of this Delphi study combined with information gained from an extensive review of the literature were used to finalize the material provided on the risk assessment aid. This risk assessment aid should be made available by future DNP cohorts for implementation in a clinical setting in an effort to improve the overall safety of anesthesia care.

Project Design

To comply with the CSUF and KPSC processes, each member of the team submitted documents for international review board (IRB) approval including Collaborative Institutional Training Initiative and Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act training certificates and Curricula Vitae. IRB approval from CSUF and KPSC was secured before the project commenced at the study facility, as shown in Appendix D. For this DNP project, information obtained from the extensive literature review and results from the three-round Delphi Study were analyzed to construct a risk assessment aid which will aid anesthesia providers in assessing and managing patients at risk for POR. The risk assessment aid consists of a risk assessment score paired with treatment recommendations. Risk assessment aids assist clinicians in making evidence-based decisions in a timely fashion, which may result in improved quality of care and decreased healthcare costs (Guerra-Farfan et al., 2022). However, the reliability of treatment

recommendations is not always evaluated, as up to 50% of guidelines have been considered untrustworthy (Guerra-Farfan et al., 2022). Relaying inaccurate information to practitioners can result in harmful, ineffective, or wasteful interventions for patients (Guerra-Farfan et al., 2022). The POR risk factors from previous DNP work were therefore further evaluated through a Delphi analysis of experts in the field, strengthening the validity of this risk assessment aid. The quality of the literature analyzed in the review of literature was graded based on the level of evidence guidelines described in Grove and Gray (2019) to mitigate threats to reliability. This DNP project used the highest level of evidence available to analyze information in the review of literature. Furthermore, conflicts of interest often exist when companies conduct research and develop guidelines (Guerra-Farfan et al., 2022). However, the members of this DNP project have no conflicts of interest to disclose. Expert panel members participating in the Delphi study were required to disclose any potential biases.

Seeking Expert Opinion Through a Delphi Study

Experts in the anesthesia community analyzed POR risk factors through the use of a Delphi study. The Delphi methodology generates a dependable consensus from a group of experts through an anonymous iterative process of questionnaires combined with controlled feedback (Nasa et al., 2021). The Delphi method was developed to structure group communication when evaluating complex problems. Its major strength is to remove inherent bias, such as group conformity and dominance, by providing anonymity of the experts involved (Nasa et al., 2021). The first application of the Delphi method was used during the Cold War by the United States army to reach a consensus among experts to predict enemy attacks (Nasa et al., 2021). Since then, it has been applied to economics, finance, and healthcare to assess information when there is an absence of well-defined testing methods.

Delphi studies have become widely used in healthcare to evaluate current knowledge, develop assessment tools, and devise management recommendation guidelines (Nasa et al., 2021). Delphi studies have been found to be particularly useful in problematic areas where research is incomplete or unavailable, such as an emerging disease or if the problem studied is a rare occurrence. Due to the nature of POR, and the need for healthcare experts' feedback, inclusion of a Delphi study strengthened the validity of this DNP project's risk assessment aid. This DNP project followed the steps shown in Figure 2, Appendix E to perform a three-round Delphi study to analyze factors related to POR for inclusion in this risk assessment aid.

Setting and Participants

Fifty-one carefully selected experts were included as participants in the Delphi study. To be considered an expert, the participants were required to have been involved in perioperative patient care, surgical care of patients, or have a baseline expertise that is related to POR. Additionally, all experts were asked questions related to their level of familiarity with the subject and were informed of the objectives of this DNP project (see Appendix F).

The Delphi study consisted of three rounds. Round one asked the experts to rate how probable it is that each identified risk factor will cause POR using the 5-point Likert scale: 1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= neutral, 4= agree, 5= strongly agree. Factors which $\geq 80\%$ experts agreed on (scoring a 4 or 5) were included in the risk assessment as this value was determined to be the minimum to reach a consensus. All the other factors were eliminated and not utilized in consecutive rounds. During round two, the experts were given the factors from round one which had received $\geq 80\%$ consensus and asked to determine if the risk factors are a minor, moderate, or high with respect to developing POR. Round three asked the experts to evaluate four risk factors which had not reached consensus ($\geq 80\%$). It included information

gathered from this DNP project's review of the literature along with definitions of the risk factor according to ACS NSQIP User Guide. Consensus among the experts was reached in the third round and the Delphi study was completed.

Data Collection

The three-round Delphi study was performed via an online survey platform, Qualtrics. All three Qualtrics surveys can be found in Appendix G. An invitation to participate in the Delphi study with a link to the anonymous Qualtrics survey was sent to participants via email. The email material sent to participants can be found in Appendix F. For each round, participants had two weeks to complete the survey with a reminder email sent out one week prior to the due date and on the date the survey was due. The first round contained 11 participants. The second round contained 12 participants. The third and final round contained 13 participants. Data from each Qualtrics survey was transferred to a password protected Google Drive that only team members could view. The data did not contain any identifying participant information. The team members then analyzed data with tables which can be found in Appendix H, Appendix I and Appendix J.

Data Analysis

Participant responses from each Delphi study were examined with simple proportional statistics to identify consensus percentages for each risk factor. Risk factors that contained $\geq 80\%$ agreement among participants were deemed to reach consensus for inclusion or exclusion from the risk assessment aid. Factors that did not reach consensus were re-evaluated using Delphi methodology of controlled anonymous feedback. The results were shared in the second and third Delphi round along with information gathered from the review of literature. In the third and final Delphi round, consensus was reached, and the Delphi study was completed.

Ethical Considerations

This project upheld the three basic principles identified by the *Belmont Report* related to research involving human subjects: Beneficence, Justice, and Respect for Persons (Tsosie et al., 2021). No specific patient identifiers were utilized to identify risk factors which contribute to POR. The ACS NSQIP database, which anonymously gathers information by trained personnel from medical charts, was utilized for this project (Liu et al., 2016).

The Delphi study obtained informed consent and participants were instructed they could choose not to answer any survey questions and may opt to withdraw from the project at any time without penalty. The Delphi study excluded participant names and other identifiers. The questions created for the survey did not contain any potentially provocative, harmful, or inflammatory rhetoric and did not elicit responses which may breach the subjects' confidentiality. The data collected was stored on a password protected Google drive accessible only to team members directly involved in the project.

Results

Delphi Study

The first round of the Delphi Study yielded a total of eleven responses out of the 51 participants included in the study. The first survey asked the participants to evaluate 23 POR risk factors. Eleven out of the 23 risk factors received either a four (agree) or a five (strongly agree) from 80% of the participants. The data was translated into tables for easier evaluation. The comprehensive list of tables can be found in Appendix H, Appendix I and Appendix J. Since these eleven risk factors were found to be highly associated with POR, they were further evaluated in the second round, where the participants were asked to classify these factors as a minor, moderate, or high risk factor for developing POR. Seven out of the eleven risk factors reached a consensus, where at least seven out of the twelve participants agreed on a risk score, and were therefore deemed suitable for inclusion in the visual aid. Four out of the eleven risk factors did not reach a consensus which therefore necessitated a third round. The third round was conducted to determine if a consensus within these last four risk factors could be obtained when the participants were provided a standard definition and information found in this DNP project's review of the literature. All risk factors evaluated in this round reached a majority, with at least six out of the thirteen participants agreeing on the factor's risk severity.

Risk Assessment Aid Infographic

Literature supports infographics as a reliable tool to effectively present information to an audience (Bystrova, 2020). Infographics are excellent in presenting information in an organized and visually appealing manner, which results in providers translating knowledge into well-informed choices. This DNP projects' risk assessment aid divides patients into three risk stratifications (mild, moderate, and severe risk) based on the results of the Delphi study. A

patient is at moderate risk if they have more than two mild or moderate risk factors. However, if the patient has more than three mild or moderate factors or one severe factor, they are classified as high risk. Subsequently, the risk aid recommends providers to choose one treatment option during each phase of the perioperative period for patients at moderate risk. For patients at severe risk, providers are recommended to choose more than six treatment recommendations with at least one during each phase of the perioperative period. The recommendations listed on the second page of the aid are founded on evidence-based on an extensive review of the literature and include preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative strategies. This DNP project followed the timeline shown in Appendix K to develop this risk assessment aid. The risk assessment aid was developed online using the platform Canva. This allowed for all team members to view and contribute. The risk assessment aid can be found in Appendix L.

Discussion

Strengths of the Project

An extensive literature review, which included 52 articles, was performed to analyze risk factors, the effectiveness of risk aids, and recommendations for providers. High-level evidence was utilized as 14 articles were qualitative, and 38 were quantitative. The quantitative studies included 9 systematic reviews, 4 RCTs, 1 observational study, 9 case-control studies, and 15 cohort studies. This large pool of research is valuable in supporting the significance of the risk aid development and the risk factors and recommendations provided.

The Delphi study received a strong response rate with 11 respondents in the first round. The participants demonstrated a diversity in years of experience, type of practice and country of residence. Furthermore, throughout the 3 rounds of the study, responses increased by 1 respondent each round, which equated to a negative attrition rate. Gargon et. al (2018) emphasizes that response rates should be prioritized as they can potentially cause attrition bias and ultimately affect the validity of the results.

Limitations of the Project

While researching recommendations for decreasing the rate of POR, there was no existing literature to guide anesthesia providers while caring for at risk patients in the perioperative setting. Subsequently, the search was broadened to include PPC, which The European Society of Anesthesiologists and European Society of Intensive Care Medicine defines as one of the following conditions: respiratory infection, respiratory failure, pleural effusion, atelectasis, pneumothorax, bronchospasm, and aspiration pneumonitis (Jammer et al., 2015). Although POR can occur from severe PPC, these terms are not synonymous and may lack direct transferability in recommendations. Additionally, a review of the literature did not yield any

information supporting the number of treatment recommendations a practitioner should utilize based on the patients' determined POR risk factor. After some discussion, this DNP project based treatment recommendations off what realistically could be implemented in the perioperative, operative, and postoperative setting. Some of the recommendations are standard practice, so this DNP project recommends choosing one treatment recommendation for each phase of the perioperative period for patients deemed moderate risk. Those that are deemed high risk should have more than six treatment recommendations implemented into their anesthetic, with at least one treatment recommendation included for each perioperative phase. The number of interventions recommended for patients at risk for POR should be explored in future projects.

While performing the Delphi study in the first round, participants received a reminder email to complete the survey. Subsequently, three participants resubmitted their responses, which were deleted after careful analysis by researchers. The following reminder emails informed participants that if they had already participated in the Qualtrics survey the researchers had received their response and they were advised to disregard the reminder.

Additionally, the recommendations included in the risk assessment aid may take time to execute for some providers, depending on the situation or location. Any urgent or emergent cases may not allow for enough time for providers to perform recommendations in the prior-to-admission or preoperative categories. Furthermore, some locations where anesthesiologists provide anesthesia may need access to resources to administer chest physiotherapy, CPAP, or HFNC. However, providers can adapt the risk aid minimum recommendations or personalize the tools available to best care for the patient.

Plans For Future Implementation

Members of this DNP project have advised Kaiser Permanente to implement the risk assessment aid and standardized recommendations to decrease the incidence of POR. This DNP project recommends that an initial baseline chart audit be performed to assess current POR incidence at facilities. Subsequently, the following measures should be assessed to measure utilization and impact of the risk assessment aid: (a) the number of patients screened with the aid, (b) the incidence of POR after implementation and (c) the number of extended observation stays or inpatient admissions. Future DNP cohorts can perform data analysis with a variety of statistical software such as Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) or Statistical Analysis Systems (SAS) with the help of a Kaiser Permanente statistician from the Regional Research Statistical Support (R2S2) or KPSA faculty.

This project recommends implementation of this risk assessment aid via educational sessions with emphasis on EBP and importance of preventing POR. Additionally, the project recommends use of visual aids in anesthesia work areas (such as the break room and anesthesia storeroom) to remind providers of the implementation. To evaluate educational effectiveness, the team should assess pre- and post-educational perceptions of POR. The future DNP team will likely utilize convenience sampling through an optional survey sent to the staff members through a work-related email to obtain feedback regarding the perceptions of the risk assessment tool. Correlational statistics and t-tests should be performed to determine the relationship between anesthesia providers' knowledge, implementation of the risk assessment aid/recommendations, and the incidence of POR. Future projects should also identify key stakeholders to aid in assessment of barriers and modifications the team may need to make to improve the implementation's compliance. Success of implementation can be evaluated by measuring

provider awareness of factors associated with POR through pre- and post- educational and compliance rate of the risk assessment aid.

Conclusion

POR is an unplanned adverse event that can occur after surgery. Improving risk identification for high-risk patients is necessary to mitigate the negative consequences such as increased morbidity, mortality, and cost associated with POR. Risk assessment aids have been shown to be reliable methods of recognizing patient risk for unwanted complications. Developing an aid with inclusion of clinically relevant recommendations was determined to be the best design as it has the potential to influence patient care through EBP. The Delphi study performed by this DNP project yielded valuable information to assemble the POR risk assessment aid by providing anonymous expert feedback. A plan for future iterations of this project has been suggested to implement this risk assessment aid into clinical practice in an effort to improve the overall safety of anesthesia.

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Appendix A

Table 1: Lewin's Change Theory

Table 1

Lewin's Change Theory

Unfreeze	Change	Refreeze
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recognize the need for change 2. Determine what needs to change 3. Encourage the replacement of old behaviors and attitudes 4. Ensure there is strong support from management 5. Manage and understand the doubts and concerns 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Plan the change 2. Implement the change 3. Help employees to learn new concept or points of view 4. Empower action 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Changes are reinforced and stabilized 2. Integrate changes into the normal way of doing things 3. Develop ways to sustain the change 4. Celebrate success

Appendix B

Figure 1: The Revised Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care

Figure 1

The Revised Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care

Note: Buckwalter, K. C., Cullen, L., Hanrahan, K., Kleiber, C., McCarthy, A. M., Rakel, B., Steelman, V., Tripp-Reimer, T., & Tucker, S. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(3), 175–182.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12223>

Appendix C

Permission to Use Iowa Model

From: Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics survey-bounce@survey.uiowa.edu
Subject: [External] Permission to Use The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care
Date: September 11, 2023 at 3:38 PM
To: grace-hingl@csu.fullerton.edu

External Email Use Caution and Confirm Sender

You have permission, as requested today, to review and/or reproduce *The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care*. Click the link below to open.

[Iowa Model - 2015.pdf](#)

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Reference: Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(3), 175-182. doi:10.1111/wvn.12223

In written material, please add the following statement:

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Please contact UIHCNursingResearchandEBP@uiowa.edu or 319-384-9098 with questions.

Appendix D

IRB Approval

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Office of Research and Sponsored Projects
P.O. Box 6850 or 1121 N. State College Blvd., 2nd Fl., Fullerton, CA 92831 / T 657-278-7719 / F 657-278-7238

APPROVAL NOTICE

From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton

March 7, 2023

From: Dr. Matt Engler-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board

To: PI: Rachel McClanahan

Application No. HSR-22-23-286
Study Title: KPSA: Reducing Postoperative Reintubations Through a Risk Assessment Aid

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 2.(i). Research that only includes interactions involving educational tests (cognitive, diagnostic, aptitude, achievement), survey procedures, interview procedures, or observation of public behavior (including visual or auditory recording).

The information obtained is recorded by the investigator in such a manner that the identity of the human subjects cannot readily be ascertained, directly or through identifiers linked to the subjects.

.

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

In addition, all research personnel must follow the institutional safety guidelines outlined for CSUF's Presidential Directive 22. Additional information can be found in the [TITANS RETURN](#); COVID-19 Recovery website.

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposal was determined to be exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation. Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-reference title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any changes in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chair of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that their responsibility for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

The institution has an Assurance on file with the Office of Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Cc: IRB Office

From: Jim X. Knell <Jim.X.Knell@kp.org>

Sent: Tuesday, January 31, 2023 5:59 PM

To: Sarah E Giron <Sarah.E.Giron@kp.org>

Subject: Reducing Postoperative Reintubations Through a Risk Assessment Aid

Good Evening Sarah,

A designated reviewer on the Kaiser Permanente Southern California (KPSC) Institutional Review Board (IRB) reviewed your submission and determined that this is not human subjects research as defined by 45 CFR 46.102 (e)(1) and (l).

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact either myself, or Marcela Sanchez at (626) 405-6124 (Tie Line 8-335-6124), my number is below.

Thank you.

Jim Knell

Research Associate
Kaiser Permanente Southern California
Institutional Review Board (IRB)
393 E. Walnut St., 4/F, NW
Pasadena, CA 91188
Tel. (626) 405-3692 /Tie Line 8-335-3692
Fax (626) 405-5186 /Tie Line 8-335-5186
KPSC IRB Intranet: <http://scalresearch.kp.org/irb/index.html>

Welcome to KPSC IRB website: <http://irb.kp-scalresearch.org>
IRB Applications / Forms website: <http://iRIS.kp-scalresearch.org>

Appendix E

Figure 2: A Delphi Study

Figure 2

A Delphi Study

Note. This model was produced to summarize the steps of a Delphi study. From “Delphi methodology in healthcare research: How to decide its appropriateness,” by P. Nasa, J. Ravi and

D. Juneja, 2021. *World Journal of Methodology* 11(4), p. 119.

Appendix F

Emails

First Round Delphi Introduction Email

Hello *Insert title/name*,

We are Student Registered Nurse Anesthetists (SRNAs) at the Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia/California State University Fullerton. We are reaching out to you in the hopes that your experience will assist us in conducting a Delphi study for inclusion in our Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) Scholarly Project. The purpose of this Delphi study is to evaluate risk factors associated with postoperative reintubation for inclusion in a perioperative risk assessment aid. You are eligible to participate in this study if you have greater than, or equal to, 5 years clinical experience and/or you have published/unpublished literature in postoperative reintubation. Should you choose to participate in this Delphi study, each online Qualtrics survey should take approximately 10 minutes to complete, with a total of three surveys. The first Qualtrics survey will ask you to provide non identifying information about yourself such as age, gender, years in practice, current position, race, ethnicity and your current type of practice. Your responses will be anonymous, and your participation in this study is completely voluntary. If you choose to participate, you may elect to discontinue participation at any time and you may choose not to answer any of the survey questions you are not comfortable with. Your completion of the three-round Delphi survey will indicate your consent to participate in this study. If you are not interested in being a part of this project, please send us an email indicating so, and we will remove you from our email list. If you are interested, the first of the three online Qualtrics surveys is linked below:

Insert Link Here

You will have two weeks to complete the survey and will receive a reminder email in a week. Please let us know if you have any questions or concerns. We may be reached at any of the following emails listed below. Thank you so much for reading this email and considering our study. We greatly appreciate your help as we attempt to improve the overall safety of anesthesia care through our work!

Sincerely,
Jacqueline Otake, SRNA
KPSA DNP Class of 2024
jacqueline.otake@csu.fullerton.edu

Caroline Tan, SRNA
KPSA DNP Class of 2024
carolit3@csu.fullerton.edu

Grace Troyer, SRNA
KPSA DNP Class of 2024

Delphi Reminder Email

Hello,

This is a reminder email that survey responses are due by *****insert date*****. For your convenience, we have reattached the survey link.

insert link here

If you have already completed the attached survey, please disregard this message. Additionally, if you would like to no longer participate in the survey, please email us with “Drop Out” noted in the email subject line. We appreciate your time and efforts as we strive to improve patient care!

Sincerely,

Jacqueline Otake, SRNA
KPSA DNP Class of 2024
jacqueline.otake@csu.fullerton.edu

Caroline Tan, SRNA
KPSA DNP Class of 2024
carolit3@csu.fullerton.edu

Grace Troyer, SRNA
KPSA DNP Class of 2024
grace-hingl@csu.fullerton.edu

Second Round Delphi Email

Hello,

We are reaching out to you again in the hopes that your experience will assist us in Round Two of our Delphi study for inclusion in our Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) Scholarly Project. To reiterate, the purpose of this Delphi study is to evaluate risk factors associated with postoperative reintubation for inclusion in a perioperative risk assessment aid. Your response will be anonymous, and your participation in this study is completely voluntary. If you choose to participate, you may elect to discontinue participation at any time and you may choose not to answer any of the survey questions you are not comfortable with. Your completion of the Delphi survey will indicate your consent to participate in this study. If you are not interested in being a part of this project, please send us an email indicating so, and we will remove you from our email list. If you are interested, the second online Qualtrics survey is linked below:

https://fullerton.qualtrics.com/jfe/form/SV_eVZHv8BESSKNmbI

You will have two weeks to complete the survey and will receive a reminder email in a week. Please let us know if you have any questions or concerns. We may be reached at any of the following emails listed below. Thank you so much for reading this email and considering our study. We greatly appreciate your help as we attempt to improve the overall safety of anesthesia care through our work!

Sincerely,

Jacqueline Otake, SRNA
KPSA DNP Class of 2024
jacqueline.otake@csu.fullerton.edu

Caroline Tan, SRNA
KPSA DNP Class of 2024
carolit3@csu.fullerton.edu

Grace Troyer, SRNA
KPSA DNP Class of 2024
grace-hingl@csu.fullerton.edu

Appendix G

Surveys

Delphi First Round Qualtrics Survey

Q1 Reducing Postoperative Reintubations Through a Risk Assessment Aid

Researchers: Jacqueline Otake, BSN RN, (860) 519-6073; Caroline Tan, BSN RN (818) 633-6486; Grace Troyer BSN RN (515) 343-0975; Rachel McClanahan DNP RN (657)278-7536

You are being asked to take part in a research study carried out by Jacqueline Otake, Caroline Tan, and Grace Troyer. This consent form explains the research study and your part in it if you decide to join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. Ask the researcher to explain anything you don't understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide to not take part in the study.

What is this study about?

The purpose of this Delphi study is to evaluate risk factors associated with postoperative reintubation for inclusion in a perioperative risk assessment aid. You are eligible to participate in this study if you have greater than, or equal to, 5 years clinical experience and/or you have published/unpublished literature in postoperative reintubation.

Taking part in the study will take about 10 minutes.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you take part in the research study, you will be asked to complete a series of Qualtrics surveys evaluating risk factors associated with postoperative reintubation over the course of several weeks. Each survey will take approximately 10 minutes to complete. You may refuse to answer any questions on the survey and your participation is completely voluntary.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

There is no direct benefit to you from being in this study.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

There are no potential risks from taking part in the study.

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential?

The data for this study will be kept anonymously. Neither the researchers nor anyone else will be able to link data to you. All survey responses will be returned anonymously. Data will be stored in a password protected computer. All researchers will have access to the anonymous survey

responses. The data for this study will be kept for 5 years for future educational use including inclusion in professional publications and presentations. The results of this study may be published or presented at professional meetings, but the identities of all research participants will remain anonymous.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study?

There will be no cost to you for taking part in this study

Whom can I contact if I have questions?

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the researcher Grace Troyer at grace-hingl@csu.fullerton.edu or (515) 343-0975. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719 or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu.

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this research study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this study. There will be no penalty for you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

What does my signature on this form mean?

Your signature on this form means that:

- You understand the information given to you in this form
- You have been able to ask the researcher questions and state any concerns
- The researcher has responded to your questions and concerns
- You believe you understand the research study and the potential benefits and risks that are involved.

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and/or have had the terms used in this consent form and their significance explained to me. By clicking below, I agree that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this project. You may print this page for your records.

Q1 Please rate the following risk factors based on how probable it is that they will cause Postoperative Reintubation (POR).

1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= neutral, 4= agree, 5= strongly agree.

POR Definition: the unplanned placement of an endotracheal tube or similar airway device within 30 days after surgery with general anesthesia (ACS NSQIP, 2015)

	1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	5 (5)
Age (1)	0	0	0	0	0
Race (2)	0	0	0	0	0
Gender (3)	0	0	0	0	0
Inpatient Status (4)	0	0	0	0	0
Smoking (5)	0	0	0	0	0
COPD (6)	0	0	0	0	0
HTN requiring medication (7)	0	0	0	0	0
CHF (8)	0	0	0	0	0
Dependent functional status (9)	0	0	0	0	0
Weight loss (10)	0	0	0	0	0
Sepsis (11)	0	0	0	0	0
Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS) (12)	0	0	0	0	0

ASA Status (13)	0	0	0	0	0
Elevated BUN (14)	0	0	0	0	0
Elevated WBC (15)	0	0	0	0	0
Dyspnea (16)	0	0	0	0	0
Anesthesia type - General (17)	0	0	0	0	0
Extended length of surgery (18)	0	0	0	0	0
Surgical blood loss (19)	0	0	0	0	0
Surgery type: Cardiac (20)	0	0	0	0	0
Surgery type: Neuro (21)	0	0	0	0	0
Surgery type: ENT (22)	0	0	0	0	0
Emergent surgery (23)	0	0	0	0	0

Delphi Second Round Qualtrics Survey

Q1 Reducing Postoperative Reintubations Through a Risk Assessment Aid

Researchers: Jacqueline Otake, BSN RN, (860) 519-6073; Caroline Tan, BSN RN (818) 633-6486; Grace Troyer BSN RN (515) 343-0975; Rachel McClanahan DNP RN (657)278-7536

You are being asked to take part in a research study carried out by Jacqueline Otake, Caroline Tan, and Grace Troyer. This consent form explains the research study and your part in it if you decide to join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. Ask the researcher to explain anything you don't understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide to not take part in the study.

What is this study about?

The purpose of this Delphi study is to evaluate risk factors associated with postoperative reintubation for inclusion in a perioperative risk assessment aid. You are eligible to participate in this study if you have greater than, or equal to, 5 years clinical experience and/or you have published/unpublished literature in postoperative reintubation.

Taking part in the study will take about 5 minutes.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you take part in the research study, you will be asked to complete a series of Qualtrics surveys evaluating risk factors associated with postoperative reintubation over the course of several weeks. Each survey will take approximately 10 minutes to complete. You may refuse to answer any questions on the survey and your participation is completely voluntary.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

There is no direct benefit to you from being in this study.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

There are no potential risks from taking part in the study.

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential?

The data for this study will be kept anonymously. Neither the researchers nor anyone else will be able to link data to you. All survey responses will be returned anonymously. Data will be stored in a password protected computer. All researchers will have access to the anonymous survey responses. The data for this study will be kept for 5 years for future educational use including inclusion in professional publications and presentations. The results of this study may be published or presented at professional meetings, but the identities of all research participants will remain anonymous.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study?

There will be no cost to you for taking part in this study. Whom can I contact if I have questions? If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the researcher Grace Troyer

at grace-hingl@csu.fullerton.edu or (515) 343-0975. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719 or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu.

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this research study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this study. There will be no penalty for you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

What does my signature on this form mean?

Your signature on this form means that:

- You understand the information given to you in this form
- The researcher has responded to your questions and concerns
- You believe you understand the research study and the potential benefits and risks that are involved.

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and/or have had the terms used in this consent form and their significance explained to me. By clicking below, I agree that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this project. You may print this page for your records.

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Q2 Based off data analyzed from the previous survey, the experts in this study found the following factors to be correlated with Postoperative Reintubation (POR). Please rate the following risk factors as:

1 = minor risk, 2 = moderate risk, 3 = major risk

POR definition: the unplanned placement of an endotracheal tube or similar airway device within 30 days after surgery with general anesthesia (ACS NSQIP, 2015)

	1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)
Emergent Surgery (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

COPD (2)	0	0	0
Sepsis (3)	0	0	0
ASA Status (4)	0	0	0
Dyspnea (5)	0	0	0
Smoking (6)	0	0	0
Cardiac Surgery (7)	0	0	0
Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS) (8)	0	0	0
General Anesthesia (9)	0	0	0
Surgical Blood Loss (10)	0	0	0
Neuro Surgery (11)	0	0	0
Extended Length of Surgery (12)	0	0	0

Delphi Third Round Qualtrics Survey

Based off data analyzed from the previous surveys, experts in this study found the following factors to be correlated with postoperative reintubation (POR). However, a consensus was not met to establish the factor as a minor risk (1), moderate risk (2), or major risk (3). Please rate the following risk factors based on your expertise and the information provided for each variable

POR definition: the unplanned placement of an endotracheal tube or similar airway device within 30 days after surgery with general anesthesia (ACS NSQIP, 2015)

Variable #1: ASA Status 3 or 4

The ACS NSQIP User Guide defines ASA classification as (1) no disturbances, (2) mild disturbances, (3) severe disturbances, (4) life threatening disturbances, (5) moribund (NSQIP, 2021).

Literature Review: Xie et al. (2022) performed a systematic review and meta-analysis to analyze risk factors associated with POR and found ASA ≥ 3 was the most prominent risk factor. Severe systemic disease impedes a patient's ability to recover from anesthesia and puts the patient at increased risk for respiratory complications, which are associated with POR (Miskovic & Lumb, 2017).

Based on your expertise and literature provided, please rate the following risk factor as a minor risk, moderate risk, or major risk for POR.

- Minor risk (1)
- Moderate risk (2)
- Severe risk (3)

Variable #2: Smoking

The ACS NSQIP User Guide defines this variable as a current smoker within one year (NSQIP, 2021)

Based on your expertise, please rate the following risk factor as a minor risk, moderate risk, or major risk for POR.

- Minor risk (1)

Moderate risk (2)

Severe risk (3)

Variable #3: Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS)

According to Stat Pearls (2023): Objectively SIRS is defined by the satisfaction of any two of the criteria below: Body temperature over 38 or under 36 degrees Celsius. Heart rate greater than 90 beats/minute Respiratory rate greater than 20 breaths/minute or partial pressure of CO2 less than 32 mmHg Leukocyte count greater than 12000 or less than 4000 /microliters or over 10% immature forms or bands.

Based on your expertise, please rate the following risk factor as a minor risk, moderate risk, or major risk for POR.

Minor risk (1)

Moderate risk (2)

Severe risk (3)

Variable #4: Surgical Blood Loss

The ACS NSQIP User Guide defines this as transfusions of red blood cells (RBCs) within the first 72 hours of surgery start time. (NSQIP, 2021)

Based on your expertise, please rate the following risk factor as a minor risk, moderate risk, or major risk for POR.

Minor risk (1)

Moderate risk (2)

Severe risk (3)

Appendix H

Delphi Round 1 Results

	Age	Race	Gender	Inpatient Status	Smoking	COPD	HTN requiring medication	CHF	Dependent functional status	Weight loss	Sepsis	Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS)
	5	3	3	4	4	4	3	4	3	3	5	4
	4	4	1	4	4	4	3	3	2	5	5	5
	1	1	1	3	4	4	2	3	4	1	4	4
	5	4	4	5	5	4	3	5	5	3	5	5
	4	3	3	4	5	5	4	5	5	3	5	4
	4	3	3	4	5	5	4	4	5	3	4	4
	4	3	5	4	4	5	4	4	4	4	4	4
	1	1	1	2	2	4	2	2	1	1	4	4
	3	3	2	4	5	5	4	5	5	3	4	4
	4			4	4		4	4	4		4	4
	4	4	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	3	5	4
Percentage agreeing 4 or 5 (sample size 11)	72%	27%	27%	72%	90%	90%	54%	72%	72%	18%	100%	100%
Included in round 2?	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes

	ASA Status	Elevated BUN	Elevated WBC	Dyspnea	Anesthesia Type-General	Extended length of surgery	Surgical blood loss	Surgery type: Cardiac	Surgery type: Neuro	Surgery type: ENT	Emergent surgery
	4	4	4	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	5
	4	2	3	4	5	3	4	4	2	1	5
	5	4	2	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5
	5	3	3	5	5	4	4	4	3	5	5
	5	4	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5
	5	4	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
	3	2	2	4	2	2	3	4	4	2	4
	4	3	3	4	3	4	3	4	4	3	4
	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
	5	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	5
Percentage agreeing 4 or 5 (sample size 11)	90%	45%	36%	100%	81%	81%	81%	100%	72%	63%	100%
Included in round 2?	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes

Appendix I

Delphi Round 2 Results

	Emergent Surgery	COPD	Sepsis	ASA Status	Dyspnea	Smoking	Cardiac Surgery
Amount of 3	7	3	7	5	4	2	2
Amount of 2	4	8	4	5	8	6	7
Amount of 1	1	1	1	2	0	4	3
Highest Consensus	58%	66%	58%	41%	66%	50%	58%
Did the Delphi Study yield a majority?	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Does the literature review back this up?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes (Backs up "Severe")	Yes	Yes	No
Severity?	Severe	Moderate	Severe	Determine in Round 3	Moderate	Determine in Round 3	Moderate

	Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS)	General Anesthesia	Surgical Blood Loss	Extended Length of Surgery
Amount of 3	4	1	0	4
Amount of 2	4	4	6	7
Amount of 1	4	7	6	1
Highest Consensus	33%	58%	50%	58%
Did the Delphi Study yield a majority?	No	Yes	No	Yes
Does the literature review back this up?	Not enough information	yes	Not enough information	Yes
Severity?	Determine in Round 3	Mild	Determine in Round 3	Moderate

Appendix J

Delphi Round 3 Results

	ASA Status 3 or 4	Smoking	Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS)	Surgical Blood Loss
Amount of Severe (3)	5	4	5	2
Amount of Moderate (2)	7	7	6	5
Amount of Minor (1)	1	2	2	6
Highest Consensus (%)	54%	54%	46%	46%
Should include in Infographic according to Delphi?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Severity?	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Minor

Appendix L

Risk Assessment Aid

POSTOPERATIVE REINTUBATION (POR) RISK ASSESSMENT AID

POR definition: unplanned placement of an endotracheal tube or similar airway device within 30 days after surgery with general anesthesia (ACS NSQIP, 2015)

RISK STRATIFICATION

MILD

- GENERAL ANESTHESIA
- SURGICAL BLOOD LOSS

MODERATE

- COPD
- DYSPNEA
- SMOKING
- CARDIAC SURGERY
- EXTENDED LENGTH OF SURGERY
- ASA STATUS 3 OR HIGHER
- SYSTEMIC INFLAMMATORY RESPONSE SYNDROME

SEVERE

- EMERGENT SURGERY
- SEPSIS

MODERATE RISK: >2 MILD OR MODERATE RISK FACTORS

HIGH RISK: >3 MILD/MODERATE RISK FACTORS OR 1 SEVERE RISK FACTOR

TREATMENT RECOMMENDATIONS

Moderate risk: chose one treatment during each phase of the perioperative period

High risk: chose > 6 treatments, one during each phase of the perioperative period

*indicates highly supported recommendations

TREATMENT RECOMMENDATIONS CONT.

• Prior to Admission

- Utilize a risk assessment tool
- Smoking cessation 4 weeks before surgery
- CXR- consider postponing elective surgery if findings are abnormal
- Inspiratory muscle training using incentive spirometry 2 weeks before surgery
- Optimize severe anemia

• Preoperative

- Targeted treatment for pulmonary diseases (CPAP for OSA, Salbutamol for asthma)
- 30 minutes of prophylactic chest physiotherapy

• Intraoperative

- Type of anesthetic: avoid GA and ETT for high-risk patients
 - Alternatives: regional anesthesia, LMA
 - If GA with ETT is necessary: use low tidal volumes (6-8 ml/kg) with PEEP of 5 cmH₂O.
 - Add recruitment maneuvers and increase PEEP if ventilation is inadequate
- Neuromuscular blockade: use short/intermediate agents, utilize nerve stimulator to assess the level of block, reverse with Sugammadex*
- Goal-directed fluid management

• Postoperative

- Prophylactic CPAP or HFNC after major abdominal and thoracic surgery
- CPAP during the initial postoperative period for OSA patients
- Mobilization and clearance of secretions: elevate the head of the bed, consider prophylactic mucolytic treatment, encourage early ambulation
- Ensure adequate pain control: utilize regional anesthesia to decrease the amount of narcotics administered

